

ANALYSIS OF THE PHENOMENON OF RESENTMENT AND ITS FEATURES

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the analysis and degree of study of the phenomenon of resentment and its relationship with the characterological features of personality in psychological literature. A comparative analysis of various approaches to the study of feelings of resentment and its significance and impact on the well-being of the individual is carried out.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена анализу и степени изученности феномена обиды и его взаимосвязи с характерологическими особенностями личности в психологической литературе. Проведен сравнительный анализ различных подходов к изучению чувства обиды и его значимости и влияния на благополучие индивида.

Key words: resentment, phenomenon, personality, emotions, feelings, behavior.

Emotions and feelings are one of the main indicators that we are living beings. The emotional sphere is a litmus paper that answers the question “how do we live?” Emotional states can motivate for great accomplishments, they can also lead the body and the social sphere of a person to complete destabilization. Different emotions, according to the degree of their strength, affect the psyche in different ways, for example, anger gives its momentary results by destroying various areas of the personality. But such feelings as guilt, resentment have their long-term impact. The study of the phenomenon of resentment in science has led to polar concepts of defining both positive and negative feelings. The consequences of the appearance of resentment can be violations of social contact, it stimulates a person to restore it, being a positive regulator in social interaction. The polar side of the negative consequences is that frequent grievances can contribute to withdrawing into oneself, into one's experiences, becoming fixed, develop into resentment as a property of a person and a character trait, up to its pathological manifestations.

Based on the methodological problem of the science of psychology, each school considered resentment according to the characteristics of the subject of study. First of all, the nature of frustration and disappointment began to be studied according to the manifestations of the psychodynamic directions of psychology. Freud lyrically defined resentment as pain experienced in silence. If for some reason the response to the trauma is not carried out, the trauma retains its primary affect, and the person

does not get rid of strong arousal by "reacting", there is a possibility that this state will become a mental trauma for him. Freud: "If in response to an insult there is nothing in response, there will be notes different from those to which there was no answer and which were accompanied by silence, unrequited longing will be described as "frustration." In some cases, affect changes the appearance of a person, freezes in it and turns into a new quality: "touchiness." According to Freud, the phenomenon of touchiness is specific to hysterical personalities⁴⁴

Anna Freud, who studied the affective life of children, noted that resentment is easily formed in childhood, especially when another child is born in the family. The older child is outraged by the increased attention that the baby receives against his will. He feels betrayed and abandoned. To attract attention, he competes with the younger for the right to get wet, dirty and even take the breast. In some cases, affect can cause various disorders: sleep, eating, bedwetting, uncontrolled defecation, fits of anger, and a number of other moral problems.

Thus, if the parents do not take control of the situation in time, the affect may become stronger, and the person may become prone to resentment.

According to Karen Horney,⁴⁵ the feeling of resentment does not disappear in youth, but remains hidden throughout life, that is, it becomes an integral part of a person's quality. A person always wants to be loved and feels pain. He becomes frustrated when those around him do not comply with his unconscious demands, such as when they are not grateful for his efforts to win the hearts of those around him. The usual reaction to being frustrated by his demands is not anger, but rather pity for his relatively unfair treatment.

Horney shows the relationship between guilt and resentment in her work. Self-reproach and self-criticism cause the greatest suffering. He begins to blame himself for some life difficulties, immediately remembers the mistreatment of him and gets involved in these events. In this way, the feeling of "I am the victim" becomes a strategic position that defends and defends with all zeal from feelings of self-loathing. Usually offended do not accept outside help, because it destroys the position of the victim.

Passive expression of self-hatred can have much deeper roots than resentment. A person transfers his internal experiences to the external world, creating a relatively peaceful attitude towards himself. In doing so, he becomes a noble victim and sufferer in a cruel, ignoble world. Thus, resentment is a manipulative trait of a person that encourages others to "force" him to show his love.

In the transactional analysis of Berne E., resentment is defined as a form of personality behavior from the perspective of a child. A "favorite" emotion is formed

⁴⁴ Фрейд З. Истерия и страх / пер. с нем. А. М. Боковинова. М.: ООО «Фирма СТД», 2006. 320 с

⁴⁵ Фрейд З. Истерия и страх / пер. с нем. А. М. Боковинова. М.: ООО «Фирма СТД», 2006. 320 с

in a child under 10 years old and dominates throughout his life. At first, as an "experiment", the child alternately experiences anger, guilt, resentment, fear, etc. If the child likes the feeling of upset, then this feeling will strengthen in him. In the future, a person will collect and disassemble his grievances.

Some remember this rarely, while others out of boredom; there are those who are looking for one reason to be upset, remember all the insults and bullying, and, finally, “explode” to express their feelings to everyone. Some people like to keep these feelings to themselves, while others like to constantly show them to others.

According to Berne, every time a person receives and collects "psychological coupons", he eventually calculates with these coupons for a specific action. Thus, individual A accumulates "coupons" of frustration over a long period of time, and sometimes deliberately "earns" them in order to be able to exclaim in front of others that he suffered enough to explode. After A has spent all his "coupons", everything starts over again: he collects his frustrations again and explodes again.

Sometimes people like to show each other their collection of grievances and pains, comparing them, whose more or less. For example, some communities can be compared to an exhibition hall where people show their psychological "coupons", discuss and evaluate the behavior of one or another acquaintance in discussions.

When we talk about resentment as a property of a personality, we also refer to the factor theory of Cattell R.⁴⁶, who understands personality as a complex structure of emotions, the origins of which are different, and relatively stable emotions are formed by the environment. The stability of the latter is weaker, and is based on the product of the interaction of emotions. According to Cattell, emotionality is a dynamic characteristic of a person, formed as a result of the action of sociocultural environmental factors, and not psychological dominants.

Resentment causes a person to pay attention to certain objects or classes of objects, feel them and react in a certain way. It is important to note that resentment is not only a personality trait, but becomes a character trait when it is clearly manifested, closely related to other characteristics, and systematically manifested in activity. In addition, resentment is a personality characteristic of having an "attractive stimulus form" that acts as a catalyst and manifests itself immediately.

Gestaltists⁴⁷ refer to the feeling of resentment as an emotion related to unfinished situations, which cannot be understood correctly without appreciating the significance of the clinging relationship. A clinging person cannot let go of his prey, refuse it, he is not able to successfully deal with the one who has become the object of his fixation: intensifying the “sucking”, he does not stop trying to extract something from the already exhausted relationship, without receiving more

⁴⁶ Холл К. С., Линдсей Г. Теории личности / Пер. с англ. И. Гриншпун. М.: Психотерапия, 2008. 656 р

⁴⁷ Хорни К. Невротическая личность нашего времени-М., 1993. -480 р

satisfaction, but only exhausting himself and increasing the feeling of resentment. In such a relationship, there is no separation into figure and ground; instead, they merge.

Gestalt psychologist Frederick Perls considers resentment to be a sign of attachment disorder. As Perls writes in *Experiments in the Psychology of Self-Knowledge*: “If the union between A and B is broken, either A thinks I broke it or B broke it, then naturally one of them is to blame. If A assumes that she did it herself, she must change the situation and apologize to B in order to re-establish the connection; if he finds B guilty, then B must pay for it or be prepared to suffer the punishment of an apology.”

To offend,” Perls writes, “means to demand that the other person feel guilty” [9, p.230]. According to Perls, guilt and resentment are two sides of the same coin, that is, they are interconnected. The purpose of unconscious demands on oneself or others is to restore the broken harmony, and restore it. But at the same time, a person as a person avoids the actual form of communication with another person (anger, understanding, etc.). When this emotional connection without any attachment - as a certain attachment - is severed, they are completely and irrevocably de-energized.

Max Scheler defines “resentment” (this term can be translated as insult and as revenge) contains impotence, helplessness, impossibility to realize insult here and now⁴⁸

In the work of Apunevich O.A. devoted to the study of resentment in adolescence, she gives a follow-up definition of resentment - "a negative emotional state experienced as injustice and helplessness, resulting from a mismatch between expectations and the real behavior of subjects in interaction, in situations of personal significance" ⁴⁹.

She also defines resentment as a property of a person that is realized in behavior, while resentment occurs even in those situations where there is a minimal discrepancy between the expectations and the real behavior of a person who is perceived as an offender. According to the proposed typology of grievances, the following types are distinguished: according to the degree of awareness (conscious and unconscious), according to duration (short-term and long-term), according to the features (forms) of manifestation (open and hidden), according to the type of reality of the source (real and imaginary, fictional) , according to the time of occurrence (present and past), according to the focus on the object (resentment towards oneself, towards another towards the group), according to the activity of manifestation (accompanied by active actions and leading to inaction), according to the degree of deviation from the norm (normative as a normal regulator of relationships or

⁴⁸ Шелер М. Ресентимент в структуре моралей. - СПб.: Наука: Университетская книга, 1999. - 231 с (p.15-19)

⁴⁹ Апуневич О. А. Коррекция обиды и обидчивости в подростковом возрасте // Психологическая коррекция как фактор обеспечения безопасности развития личности. - Череповец: Изд-во ЧГУ, 2011. -р. 44-95.

pathological, included in various types of deviant behavior), according to the possibilities of correction (correctable and non-correctable)⁵⁰.

Apunevich O.A. singles out the psychological functions of resentment: signal (resentment “signals” about violations of social communications), evaluative (resentment shows how much contact is broken), regulatory (controls and corrects communications), adaptive (resentment helps to overcome a difficult situation, avoid responsibility through resentment), incentive (shows a concrete path to the restoration of broken relationships), communicative (an offended person attracts the attention or even sympathy of others)⁵¹

Gusakov N.Yu. interprets resentment as a psychological process. That is, resentment is not only an emotional reaction to an event that is assessed as unfair, but also a process in which there is a goal, a procedure and a result. That is, in the actions of the offended one can distinguish: 1) the presence of a goal (“the actions of the offended person are not spontaneous or chaotic, but quite consistent and logical”, i.e., expedient); 2) the offended person has self-value for himself (ideas of self-worth); 3) the presence in the picture of the world of the offended person of the idea of justice / injustice; 4) the presence of an unfair (insulting, insulting) action; 5) awareness of the fact of an unfair (offensive) action.⁵² According to Gusakov N.Yu., resentment is the humiliated dignity of a person or an unfulfilled need for his recognition⁵³

Ilyin E.P. in his work “Emotions and Feelings” defines resentment as “a frustration emotion” and “an emotional reaction to an unfair attitude towards oneself ... when a person’s self-esteem is hurt, when a person realizes that he is undeservedly humiliated”⁵⁴. Orlov Yu. M. defines resentment as a “painful emotion”⁵⁵

As part of his study "Features of resolving intrapersonal conflict among students during their studies at the university" Gurov A.V. drew parallels between dependence, feelings of resentment, guilt and loneliness with intrapersonal conflicts.

The basis of our study was the Pedagogical University students of the first second and second year, between the age of 18 and 20. The results of studies on the methods of indicators and forms of aggression by Bass A. and Darkey A. and the Test for resentment have become quite contradictory for us, in which the features of the manifestation of resentment and resentment have been revealed. The methodology for determining Bass-Darkey's aggressiveness in percentage terms revealed high

⁵⁰ Апуневич О. А. Коррекция обиды и обидчивости в подростковом возрасте // Психологическая коррекция как фактор обеспечения безопасности развития личности. - Череповец: Изд-во ЧГУ, 2011. – р.47.

⁵¹ Апуневич О. А. Коррекция обиды и обидчивости в подростковом возрасте // Психологическая коррекция как фактор обеспечения безопасности развития личности. - Череповец: Изд-во ЧГУ, 2011. - р. 46-47.

⁵² Бганба М. Ч. Прямые и косвенные номинации концепта «обида» в английском языке: дис. ... канд. филол. наук. - М., 2010. - 217 с.

⁵³ Бганба М. Ч. Прямые и косвенные номинации концепта «обида» в английском языке: дис. ... канд. филол. наук. - М., 2010. - 217 р.

⁵⁴ Ильин Е. П. Эмоции и чувства. - СПб.: Питер, 2001. - 752 р(165 р)

⁵⁵ Орлов Ю. М. Обида. Вина. - М.: Слайдинг, 2004. - 96 с.

indicators of the scale of resentment only in 11% of the respondents. But the results of the methodology for determining touchiness showed 26% in the same sample with a high level of touchiness.

According to Apunevich O., resentment is a destructive feeling, and resentment is a permanent manifestation of character. It can be concluded that in student age, resentment as a destructive feeling is not manifested in a large number of youth of adolescence age, and resentment as a characterological quality is more common.

Based on the foregoing, the feeling of resentment, this is a complex emotional state regarded as both destructive and having constructive consequences, this state, manifested in behavior, can have many causes. The results of our study showed that resentment and resentment as a personality characteristic may not have a direct and inverse relationship.

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